

BMP15 genetic variations in patients with premature ovarian insufficiency – correlation with clinical and laboratory parameters

Petya Andreeva^{1,2}, Kalina Mihova³, Radka Tafradjiiska-Hadjiolova⁴, Ivanka Dimova^{3,5}

¹ Shterev Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria

² South-West University, Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria

³ Molecular Medicine Center, Medical University Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

⁴ Department of Physiology and Pathophysiology, Medical University Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

⁵ Department of Medical Genetics, Medical University Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding authors: Petya Andreeva (petya.andreeva@swu.bg); Ivelina Oprova (ivelina.oprova@gmail.com)

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Abstract

Objective: Bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP15) is an oocyte-specific protein with essential functions on early folliculogenesis, a regulator of granulosa cell growth and differentiation. Recognizing the significant role of BMP15 in the development of Premature Ovarian Insufficiency (POI), our objective was to study the incidence of its genetic variants in a group of Bulgarian women affected by POI and to correlate them with clinical-laboratory parameters of the patients.

Materials and methods: Direct Sanger sequencing of the BMP15 gene was performed in 37 patients with POI. The prevalence of the variants was compared to the internal database with unselected Bulgarian individuals.

Results: In 56.8% of the patients, we detected one or two of the following variants c.-9C>G, c.308A>G, c.852C>T and c.538G>A. A significantly increased frequency of heterozygotes for variants c.-9C>G (40.5%) and c.308A>G (29.7%) was established in POI patients. We found that the combined carriership of these two frequent variants is significantly associated with the increased levels of FSH and the duration of amenorrhea, in Bulgarian patients with POI.

Conclusion: Our study underscores the significant role of BMP15 as a crucial candidate gene and emphasizes the need for investigations in diverse population groups for its inclusion in the algorithm for early diagnostics and management of patients with POI.

Keywords

allele and genotype frequencies, Bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP15), genetic variations, Premature Ovarian Insufficiency (POI)

Introduction

Premature ovarian insufficiency (POI) is a complex and not yet understood condition with heterogeneous etiology and multisystem consequences resulting from premature ovarian aging. This is a common cause of infertility, characterized by amenorrhea, hypogonadism, and elevated gonadotropin levels in women under 40 years of age. POI has gained attention over the past two decades after it became apparent that it was not an extremely rare disorder. Recognition and management of POI is becoming increasingly important as women postpone their reproductive plans. Due to its heterogeneous nature and different mechanisms of occurrence, elucidation of the cause of POI is a key point in the diagnosis and treatment of affected patients. Although the underlying cause remains unexplained in most cases, various data show that POI has a strong genetic component (Dixit et al. 2010; Kumar et al. 2017). Different X chromosome deletions and balanced translocations between the X chromosome and autosomes have been observed in individuals suffering from POI. The most prevalent genetic aberration in POI is the FMR1 permutation, which is followed by abnormalities in the bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP15) gene (Galloway et al. 2000; Yan et al. 2001; Simpson et al. 2008).

BMP15 gene, situated on chromosome Xp11.2, was initially linked to its involvement in the development of POI and is responsible for the synthesis of an oocyte-specific protein with essential functions on early folliculogenesis, a regulator of granulosa cell growth and differentiation. Along with growth/differentiation factor 9 (GDF9), it plays a crucial role in the ovary of mono- or polyovulates and in the normal development of the embryo or fetus as a homodimer or heterodimer (Persani et al. 2010; Afkhami et al. 2022).

Recognizing the significant role of *BMP15* in the development of POI, our objective was to study the incidence of genetic variants in this gene in a group of Bulgarian women affected by POI by gene sequencing analysis. Doing this, we carried out an extensive correlation analysis between the found *BMP15* genetic changes and clinical-laboratory parameters of the patients, as well. Our ultimate goal is to create an optimal algorithm for early detection and management of this condition to improve the reproductive health care in our patients.

Materials and methods

Patients

Approval for this research was obtained from the Ethics Committee of "Shterev Hospital", Sofia, Bulgaria. Prior to their involvement in the study, all participants provided written informed consent. A comprehensive clinical evaluation, including physical examinations, blood tests, and sonography, was carried out as part of the standard clinical procedure by skilled gynecologists. Hormone analyses and antral follicle count (AFC) were performed to outline the patients with ovarian failure. The study included

thirty-seven women with normal karyotypes who had idiopathic secondary amenorrhea before reaching the age of 40. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are given below.

Inclusion criteria: women over 18 to 40 years of age, with normal female karyotype from previous cytogenetic analysis, absence of operative interventions in the area of the ovaries, with normal thyroid function as evidenced by normal serum TSH levels, there are no other causes of female infertility in the subject, and no history of past or current malignancy. And diagnosed premature ovarian failure: at least two menopausal FSH levels (≥ 25 IU/L) and/or primary or secondary amenorrhea for at least 4 months OR a diagnosis of reduced ovarian reserve defined as AMH < 0.5 ng/mL and FSH > 20 IU/L and/or failure of prior attempts at assisted reproductive techniques (ART) due to limited ovarian response (poor ovarian response).

DNA extraction and sequencing

Genomic DNA was isolated from whole blood samples using the salting-out technique. The quality and concentration of the extracted DNA were assessed through spectrophotometry. Specific primer sets were designed for two exons of the *BMP15* gene with the assistance of Oligo Explorer and Primer Express software. Analysis of the entire sequence of the *BMP15* gene, encompassing its two exons and the exon-intron junctions, was carried out using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method. Subsequently, Sanger sequencing was performed using the Big-Dye[®] Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit from Applied Biosystems[®] (Life Technologies). The obtained sequences were scrutinized through ABI Sequencing Analysis v5.3 software and compared to the reference NM_001114767.2 available at <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>. All sequence variations were cross-referenced with the Exome Variant Server and the ExAC database (exac.broadinstitute.org/).

In silico analysis

To assess their impact on the structure and function of *BMP15*, in silico predictions were conducted using tools such as PolyPhen-2 (<http://genetics.bwh.harvard.edu/>), Pro{Citation}vean (provean.jcvi.org/), and SIFT (sift.jcvi.org/). The pathogenicity of these variants was further evaluated using the Mutation Taster tool (www.mutation-taster.org/). The prevalence of the variants was checked on the database of Laboratory of Genomic diagnostics, Molecular Medicine Center, representing whole/targeted exome sequencing data of 485 Bulgarian individuals from with the approximate 1:1 Female/Male ratio.

Statistical analyses

The clinical data gathered were subject to statistical analysis using SPSS version 24, with a predetermined significance level of 5%. Quantitative data were assessed for correlations through ANOVA, while qualitative data were analyzed using chi-square tests to explore potential relationships.

Results

Direct Sanger sequencing of the *BMP15* gene was performed in 37 patients with POI. No pathogenic mutations were identified, only polymorphisms and variants of unclear significance. The frequency of two polymorphisms in the gene related to the development of POI was identified using the sequencing data: c.-9C>G (rs3810682) and c.308A>G, p.Asn103Ser (rs41308602). This incidence in female patients was compared with the frequency of the two polymorphisms in the Bulgarian population—data were extracted from clinical exome sequencing in 485 unselected Bulgarian patients. In parallel, a comparison was made with population genetic data for Europe and the world from publicly shared genomic databases.

Electropherograms of heterozygous and homozygous for rs3810682 and heterozygous for rs41308602 are demonstrated in Fig. 1.

Wild-type alleles were found in 16 of the examined patients (43.2%); of the remaining 56.8%, seven were heterozygous carriers (18.9%), and one was homozygous (2.7%) only for variant rs3810682; eight were heterozygous carriers of both two variants rs3810682 and rs41308602 (21.6%); three were both homozygous for rs3810682 and heterozygous for rs41308602 (8.1%); one patient each (2.7%) was a carrier of variant rs104894767 (c.538G>A, p.Ala180Thr) and rs17003221 (c.852C>T) (Fig. 2). The results of the analysis are presented in Table 1.

A significantly increased frequency of heterozygotes for rs3810682 and rs41308602 polymorphisms was found in POI patients compared to the frequency in the Bulgarian population, and the difference was even more significant when compared to the worldwide frequency. We also found a statistically significantly higher frequency of the alternative G allele in the rs41308602 polymorphism (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Allele and genotype frequencies for the analysed *BMP15* polymorphisms.

Polymorphism	Frequency in POI (%)	Frequency in BG (%)	Frequency in Ensemble genome browser (%)
rs3810682 G allele	32.90%	23.20%	15.10% 11.80%
CG heterozygotes	40.50%*	19.60%*	
GG homozygotes	10.80%	13.40%	1.80%
rs41308602 G allele	14.90%**	6.20%**	2.80%
AG heterozygotes	29.70%***	5.80%***	2.70%
GG homozygotes	0.00%	3.30%	0.20%

* $p < 0.002$; ** $p < 0.04$; *** $p < 0.0001$.

Table 2 presents the clinical and laboratory data of the patients who are carriers of the polymorphisms and the wild-type alleles. For the carriers of rs3810682, the average age was 33.4 years, a BMI of 22.2, and a duration of amenorrhea of 39.2 months; the average hormone levels were as follows: FSH—44.1 IU/l; LH—17.6 IU/l; AMH—0.45 ng/mL; E2—179.6 pmol/l; T—1.69 ng/mL; DHEA-S—4.8 μ mol/l; the mean antral follicle count was 3.2. Carriers of rs41308602 had an average age of thirty-five years, a BMI of 22.3, an average duration of amenorrhea of 54.5 months, with the following hormone levels: FSH—61.5 IU/l; LH—25.4 IU/l; AMH—0.39 ng/mL; E2—195.5 pmol/l; T—0.68 ng/mL; DHEA-S—4.6 mol/l; the mean antral follicle count—3.2. For patients with wild-type *BMP15* alleles, the average age was 33.3 years, BMI was 20.9, and the duration of amenorrhea was 21.6 months; average hormone levels were as follows: FSH—25.4 IU/l; LH—19.1 IU/l; AMH—1.8 ng/mL; E2—210.5 pmol/l; T—0.42 ng/mL; and DHEA-S—4.4 mol/l; AFC—3.7.

FSH levels in carriers of both variants were considerably greater. There was a trend for a significant difference in amenorrhea duration ($p < 0.08$), which was longer in

Figure 1. Electropherograms showing hetero- and homozygote for the genetic variant rs3810682 (top) and heterozygote for the genetic variant rs41308602 (bottom).

Figure 2. *BMP15* genetic variations in Bulgarian POI patients.

Figure 3. Allele and genotype frequencies for rs3810682 and rs41308602 in patients and control populations.

women carrying the *BMP15* variant rs41308602 than in individuals carrying the wild-type genotype (54.5 vs. 21.6 months). There was no statistically significant difference in oestradiol, AMH, testosterone, and DHEA levels, as well as body mass index and antral follicle count.

Two other polymorphisms were found in two patients: rs104894767 (c.538G>A, p.Ala180Thr) with a very low frequency in the database (<0.01) and rs17003221 (c.852C>T) with an average frequency of the alternative allele of 0.18. The carrier of the first variant was 27 years old with a BMI of 25, AMH—0.008 ng/mL, oestradiol—21.1 pmol/l, FSH—31.2 IU/l, LH—45.1 IU/l; number of antral follicles—1 and a duration of amenorrhea of 72 months (Table 3). The carrier of the second variant was 33 years old with a BMI of 31, AMH—0.29 ng/mL, oestradiol—230 pmol/l, FSH—17.9 IU/l, LH—14 IU/l; number of antral follicles—2 and a duration of amenorrhea of 6 months (Table 3).

We analyzed the individual and combined carriership of variants in *BMP15*, as 7 patients were heterozygous for rs3810682 only, one patient was homozygous for this variant only, 3 patients were homozygous for rs3810682 and heterozygous for rs41308602, 8 patients were heterozygous for both variants rs3810682 and rs41308602, and one patient each was found to carry rs104894767

Table 2. Clinical-laboratory parameters of the patients—carriers of genetic variants and wild-type alleles (average values).

Parameter	Carriers of <i>BMP15</i> rs3810682	Carriers of <i>BMP15</i> rs41308602	Wild type <i>BMP15</i> alleles	
Age	33.4	35.5	33.3	ns
BMI	22.2	22.3	20.9	ns
Amenorrhea (months)	39.2	54.5*	21.6*	*p<0.08
FSH	*44.1	61.5**	*25.4**	*p<0.05 **p<0.005
LH	17.6	25.4	19.1	ns
AMH	0.45	0.39	0.49	ns
E2	179.6	195.5	210.5	ns
T	0.69	0.68	0.42	ns
DHEA-S	4.8	4.6	4.4	ns
AFC	3.2	3.2	3.7	ns

and rs17003221 variants. No patient was an independent carrier of the rs41308602 variant. Table 3 summarizes the mean values of the clinical parameters in the groups listed above.

AMH levels were lowest in the rs104894767 carrier, the simultaneous rs3810682/rs41308602 heterozygotes and the rs3810682 homozygote, amenorrhea was longest for rs104894767, simultaneous homozygotes rs3810682/

Table 3. Clinical-laboratory parameters in the groups with single and combined carriers of *BMP15* variants and in wild-type patients.

Group	Age	FSH	LH	AMH	E2	T	DHEA- S	AFC	Amenorrhea (months)	BMI
Heterozygotes rs3810682	29.4	20.5	7.6	0.5	163.6	0.7	5.2	3.2	28.6	23.7
Homozygote rs3810682	38	18.4	10.2	0.33	221	0.55	4.57	5	2	20
Homozygotes rs3810682/ Heterozygotes rs41308602	35.7	52.5	21	0.1	139	0.7	6.9	1.7	62.3	25
Heterozygotes for both variants	35.5	64.9	27	0.5	216.7	0.65	3.7	3.8	67.3	21.3
rs104894767	27	31.2	45.1	0.008	21.1	NA	4.25	1	72	25
rs17003221	33	17.9	14	0.29	230	NA	NA	2	6	31
Wild type	33.3	25.4	19.1	1.8	210.5	0.42	4.4	3.7	21.6	20.9

heterozygotes rs41308602 and simultaneous heterozygotes for both variants. The lowest number of antral follicles was observed with rs104894767 and rs3810682 homozygotes/rs41308602 heterozygotes. Combined carriers of rs3810682 and rs41308602 have the highest levels of FSH ($p < 0.01$) and the highest duration of amenorrhea ($p < 0.08$) (Figs 4, 5).

Figure 5. Duration of amenorrhea in single and combined carriers of genetic variants in comparison to wild-type patients.

Discussion

In this research, we conducted a detailed molecular examination of the *BMP15* gene in a group of unrelated Bulgarian women who were diagnosed with idiopathic premature ovarian insufficiency (POI). Persani and colleagues conducted a comprehensive review of published data prior

to 2014, and their analysis revealed that the occurrence of genetic variants in the *BMP15* gene was 4.5% among individuals diagnosed with POI, in stark contrast to the mere 0.43% prevalence observed in women with typical ovarian function (Persani et al. 2014). Not long ago, the first causative mutation in the *BMP15* gene (specifically, a heterozygous mutation at position Y235C, affecting the pro domain of the corresponding protein) was discovered in two Italian sisters experiencing hypergonadotropic ovarian failure (Di Pascale et al. 2004). Intriguingly, they inherited this genetic alteration from their father, who remained in good health. In laboratory experiments, researchers observed that this mutated *BMP15* variant was linked to a decrease in granulosa cell (GC) growth, likely resulting from an abnormal processing of the mutated protein. Subsequently, additional mutations in the *BMP15* gene were identified in a broader study that encompassed individuals with ovarian failure, and more than ten mutations in the *BMP15* gene have been linked to POI (Di Pasquale et al. 2004; Di Pasquale et al. 2006; Dixit et al. 2006; Laissue et al. 2006; Rossetti et al. 2009; Tiotiu et al. 2010; Laissue et al. 2015). There is an ongoing discussion, however, about whether all the *BMP15* variants that have been documented truly play a significant role in the development of the disease in question.

We detected four variants in the gene: three common (c.-9C>G, rs3810682; c.308A>G, p.N103S, rs41308602; c.852C>T, p.S284=, rs17003221) and one rare allele (c.538G>A, p.A180T, rs104894767). The first two variants, c.-9 C>G and p.N103S, are very well-documented, both in individuals with the condition and in healthy controls (Dixit et al. 2006; Abir et al. 2011; Al-ajoury et al. 2015). They are listed in the ClinVar database as benign variants, linked to ovarian dysgenesis. Regarding their frequency, the 5'-UTR variant c.-9

C>G has an allele frequency of 0.16 in gnomAD (ranging from 0.028 in East Asia to 0.21 in Europe). In our unselected Bulgarian cohort, the frequency of this allele was 0.23, and we found the allele frequency of 0.329 in our patients with POI. This variant was found in 51.3% of the patients, mainly in heterozygous state (40.5%) and less frequently in homozygous state (10.8%). Indeed, an analysis of the *BMP15* open reading frame, encompassing a short 5' exon 1-UTR region as well as the intron-exon boundaries, revealed that the c.-9G allele was part of a haplotype associated with Premature Ovarian Failure in a group of

202 Indian women, as Dixit and colleagues documented in 2006 (Dixit et al. 2006). In another investigation involving 398 women with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS), it was revealed that, although the c.-9C>G variant was not directly linked to the pathogenesis of the disease, it might have been associated with specific clinical characteristics, such as infertility, as reported by González et al. in 2008 (González et al. 2008). Because of the heightened responsiveness associated with the G allele, the c.-9C > G variant also displayed the capacity to enhance the response to recombinant FSH in the context of assisted reproduction techniques (Hanevik et al. 2011).

For the c.308 A>G variant, we observed that it has an allele frequency of 0.057 in gnomAD (ranging from 0 in East Asia and 0.088 in Europe) and 0.028 in the 1000 Genomes database. Our internal database showed 0.062 frequency of this allele in unselected Bulgarian individuals and statistically higher frequency of 0.15 in the patients with POI. This variant was detected in 29.7% of the patients, only in heterozygous state. Interestingly, it was always in combination with the 5' -UTR variant c.-9 C>G. This is in agreement with the finding for an association of POI with the haplotype G-G in the variants c.-9C>G and c.308A>G [8]. Moreover, we found that the combined carriership of these two frequent variants is significantly associated with the increased levels of FSH and the duration of amenorrhea. The variant *BMP15* c.-9C>G alone did not show any associations, in line with the study of Leidig et al. for the lack of association of this variant with the condition (Leidig et al. 2008).

Regarding the third common variant c.852C>T, discovered in only one patient from our study, in the existing body of literature, many authors reported that there were no significant differences in the frequencies of *BMP15* c.852C>T genotypes between the Premature Ovarian Failure and control groups (Laissue et al. 2006; Zhang et al. 2007; Tiotiu et al. 2010; Ma L et al. 2015).

We detected only in one patient the rare variant c.538G>A (A180T) as well. The interpretation of its importance remained ambiguous, as some research recognized it only in patients (Dixit et al. 2006; Laissue et al. 2006), but others found it in both individuals with and without the condition. (Dixit et al. 2006; Laissue et al. 2006; Leidig et al. 2008; Tiotiu et al. 2010). In 2017, Patiño and colleagues conducted an assessment and determined that the activity of the A180T variant was approximately one-fourth of the activity observed in the wild-type *BMP15* and observed its potential to diminish the production of mature peptide, impede activity, or disrupt synergy with GDF9 (Patiño et al. 2017). Our patient with this variant had the lowest levels of AMH and oestradiol, the lowest number of antral follicles, and the longest duration of amenorrhea.

In conclusion, the current research offers compelling proof for the association of naturally occurring genetic variations in the *BMP15* gene with premature ovarian insufficiency. The correlation with the clinical and laboratory

parameters in Bulgarian patients revealed a significant association of the combined carriership of both variants c.-9 C>G and c.308A>G with the higher FSH levels and longer duration of amenorrhea. This underscores the significant role of *BMP15* as a crucial candidate gene and emphasizes the need for its investigation in diverse population groups. Extending this investigation would allow us to suggest the inclusion of *BMP15* genotyping in the algorithm for early diagnostics and proper management of the women who are at risk for reproductive failure due to premature ovarian insufficiency.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The declarations of informed consent have been deposited in Shterev Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, I.D., P.A. and I.O.; Methodology, I.D., P.A. and I.O.; Investigation, I.D., P.A., I.O., K.M. and R.T-H.; Data curation, I.D.; Formal analysis, I.D.; Visualization I.D. and I.O.; Writing—original draft preparation, I.D. and I.O.; Writing—review and editing, I.D. and P.A.; Supervision, I.D. and P.A.

Author ORCIDs

Petya Andreeva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6277-8550>

Ivelina Oprova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1853-3994>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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